

Bacterially-promoted carbonation of lime-based building materials

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Abstract. Lime-based binders, while historically significant, exhibit low strength and slow hardening, which has led to its replacement by cement. Hardening in lime-based materials occurs primarily through carbonation, whereby $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ reacts with atmospheric CO_2 and produces CaCO_3 cement. This study explores using bacterial additives to accelerate lime hardening by producing extra CO_2 . Three bacterial species were isolated and grown in liquid media. In a closed container, lime-mortar specimens were indirectly exposed to a cotton soaked in either bacterial suspension or water. Thermogravimetric analysis after 7 and 14 days indicated increased carbonation in cubes incubated with bacterial suspension, but not significantly. Subsequently, one bacterial suspension was mixed directly with lime. Progression of carbonation was tested with phenolphthalein and after 7, 14 and 21 days faster carbonation was seen in bacteria-containing pastes than those with only culture media. Overall, bacteria can carbonate lime materials but further optimization is needed for practical application.

1 Introduction

Lime is a common binder historically used in masonry structures, offering protection and longevity to the masonry units [1]. Despite being traditionally used for millennia, the last century saw a rise in the use of Portland cement, which also replaced lime in restoration works [2]. This poses a risk to restored structures due to the incompatibility of cement with ancient traditional masonry structures [1].

One reason for the replacement of lime by cement as the binder of choice has been its faster hardening. The hardening of aerial lime mortars occurs through the reaction of hydrated lime (the mineral phase portlandite, $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$) with atmospheric CO_2 (Eq. 1-3):

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This reaction can be slow, with reports of 1700-year-old mortars still not fully carbonated [3]. Factors influencing the rate of carbonation include temperature, humidity, and CO₂ concentration. Various strategies exist to enhance this process, including the use of CO₂-producing additives, either of organic or synthetic origin [4].

A less explored area is microbial-mediated carbonation, whereby microorganisms could be used as additives to improve lime-material properties. Microorganisms possess qualities that make them attractive as additives for early hardening, particularly through the release of CO₂ by metabolising organic compounds as well as the formation of biomineralized calcite [5]. The use of microbial additives is not a new concept in cementitious materials, with extensive work happening in the field of self-healing in mortars and concrete [5]. Here we study the effects of microbial additives on the kinetics and dynamics of aerial lime carbonation.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Bacteria and growth conditions

Three alkaliphilic strains were isolated from a lime mortar wall in Horikoshi media (unpublished work) and further kept in Tryptic Soy Agar, a solid media (TSA: Pancreatic Digest of Casein 17.0 g/Lt, Peptic Digest of Soybean 3.0 g/Lt, Glucose 2.5 g/Lt, NaCl 5.0 g/Lt, 14 g/Lt Agar) (Merck, Germany). To prepare bacterial suspension, the isolates were grown in Tryptic Soy Broth, a liquid media (TSB: Pancreatic Digest of Casein 17.0 g/Lt, Peptic Digest of Soybean 3.0 g/Lt, Glucose 2.5 g/Lt, NaCl 5.0 g/Lt) (Merck, Germany) from a 1:100 fully grown inoculum and grown at 28 °C and shaken at 125 RPM for 24 h. The suspensions were then centrifuged at 1500 RCF for 10 minutes and resuspended in fresh TSB. TSB. Isolate 1, used further in this work was the only sequenced strain. It was deposited as *Schouchella clausii* (LMG 33400) at the Belgian Coordinated Collections of Microorganisms.

2.2 Carbonation of lime-mortar cubes

2.2.1 Preparation and curing of lime-mortar cubes

A lime mortar mixture was prepared using a 1:3 hydrated-lime:aggregate ratio with a water:binder ratio of 1.85. The hydrated lime was a CL 90-S (Lhoist, Belgium) and the aggregate was a silicate sand (> 98 % silica content) with standard granulometry (EN 196-1). The mortar was cast into a silicone mould with 1.4 x 1.4 x 1 cm wells. EN 1015-11 for casting of masonry mortars was adapted to the smaller samples. Briefly, a layer of gauze and 2 layers of filter paper were placed on the filled mould. A 1.5 kg of weight was applied to the mortar, and the mortar was left to rest for 1 h. Finally, the mould was placed at 100 °C for 1.5 h to fully dry the cubes. After drying, 3 lime cubes were placed inside a container. Separated from the cubes with a layer of parafilm, a cotton soaked in 10 mL of suspension was then added to the container and closed firmly. The used suspensions included three bacterial suspensions and water. After 7 and 14 days the cotton was removed and samples were analyzed.

2.2.2 Thermogravimetric analysis

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) can be used to determine the amount of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ converted to CaCO_3 in a lime mortar. TGA was done in a TGA-1000-U (Navas Instruments, USA). The whole lime cube (3.9 ± 0.2 g) was inserted into the machine and heated in a ceramic crucible in a N_2 atmosphere, at 5°C min^{-1} , from 20 to 950°C . The weight percentage (wt %) loss between 350 and 550°C was used to calculate the remaining $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ in the sample (CH_{final}) and 650 and 900°C was used to calculate the amount of CaCO_3 in the sample (CC_{final}). Given that 1 mol of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ is converted to 1 mol of CaCO_3 , by knowing CC_{final} it was possible to know how many mols and wt % of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ was converted into CaCO_3 through carbonation ($\text{CH}_{\text{carbonated}}$). The percentage of carbonation for each sample was then calculated as:

$$\text{Carbonation (\%)} = \frac{\text{CH}_{\text{carbonated}}}{\text{CH}_{\text{final}} + \text{CH}_{\text{carbonated}}} * 100$$

The average percentage of carbonation was calculated using all three samples. To compare significant differences of values between groups a one way ANOVA test ($\alpha = 0.05$) was performed on R.

2.3 Carbonation of lime-paste cubes

2.3.1 Preparation and curing of lime-paste cubes

Lime paste mixtures with either bacterial suspension or sterile TSB were prepared to study the capacity of the bacteria to carbonate the lime paste directly. Hydrate lime CL 90-S (Lhoist, Belgium) was used to prepare pastes using a 1:1 water-to-binder ratio, where the bacterial suspensions and TSB were used in place of water. The paste was mixed by hand until homogeneous and cast into silicone moulds with wells of $1.0 \times 1.4 \times 1.4 \text{ cm}^3$. The moulds were tapped to remove internal air bubbles and cured at 21°C and 65 % RH for a total of 7, 14 and 21 days. Paste samples collected at each time interval were subsequently analyzed.

2.3.2 Phenolphthalein analysis and measurement

At 7, 14 and 21 days lime cubes were split in half and at least three halves were sprayed with a 0.1 wt % ethanolic solution of phenolphthalein pH indicator. After 1 h images were taken of the samples. The carbonation front was then analysed using ImageJ image analysis software. The images were manually thresholded to select the pink (uncarbonated) or white (carbonated) regions on the sprayed samples and the percentage of carbonation was calculated as the white fraction from the total area.

3 Results and Discussion

To test the capacity of bacterially-derived CO_2 to carbonate a lime mortar, cubes were enclosed in a container with a cotton soaked either in water or one of the three bacterial suspensions from each isolate. Separate containers were used for each bacteria and water and parafilm was used as a separation between the cotton and the cubes to ensure that the cotton or bacteria didn't directly touch the cubes. Through this carbonation could only occur through CO_2 and not contamination of the cubes by the bacteria. After 7 days, lime cubes exposed to

the activity of all strains showed, on average, a higher degree of carbonation as compared with the water control, implying that there was a higher CO₂ concentration in the enclosed environment with bacteria as a result of bacterial activity (Fig. 1). At day 14 the carbonation was the same as at day 7 for all samples (Fig. 1), which meant that the increase in CO₂ occurred only within the first week. For the water control, this is sensible as likely all the CO₂ in the enclosed atmosphere was consumed. For the bacterial suspensions, this was unexpected and likely meant that the bacterial activity reduced over time, either due to consumption of the media or the death of the bacteria. Given that the bacteria are alkaliphilic, the use of TSB, which has a pH of 7.3 ± 0.2 at 25 °C, might be on the lower limit of tolerance of the bacteria leading to their early drop in activity.

Given that no significant difference was observed between isolates ($p > 0.05$), only one isolate was studied further. Isolate 1 (*Schouchella clausii* (LMG 33400) and further referred to as Sc) was chosen to be sequenced due to its lower variability of carbonation rate.

Fig. 1. Average percentage of carbonation according to TGA of lime-mortar cubes per date and tested condition. Error bars show the standard error of the average percentage carbonation of three replicates carbonated in the same environment. Nonsignificant differences ($p > 0.05$) were observed between groups.

To determine whether carbonation of the lime could be achieved with the bacteria in direct contact with the lime, lime paste cubes with water, uninoculated TSB medium or bacterial Sc suspension were prepared. The fact that the cubes were allowed to carbonate under atmospheric conditions meant that CO₂ was more readily available for the lime to carbonate and this was observed on day 7 for the pastes mixed with water (Fig. 2). Interestingly, almost no carbonation could be measured from the phenolphthalein analysis on the pastes with organics, i.e. TSB and Sc (Fig. 2). At day 14 and 21 the carbonation progressed steadily for water samples. In contrast, there was a rapid increase in carbonation, especially between day 14 and 21 for both TSB and Sc. Only at day 21 were there observable differences between the media control and the bacterial suspension, with the Sc lime pastes performing better, albeit not significantly.

A slight delay of the bacterial activity can be expected given the likely shock the bacteria are undergoing when placed in a comfortable environment such as that from the liquid culture medium into the lime paste, where the pH is expected to be ~ 12.4 . As such, by day 14 no difference was seen between TSB and Sc, but an increase in bacterial activity could appear by day 21. We note that unlike the results from the indirect carbonation (Fig. 1), here the bacteria were exposed to a higher pH, which once they have adapted to their environment, will be more suitable given their alkalophilicity. This is especially true as carbonation progresses and the pH is reduced from hyperalkaline to the moderately alkaline equilibrium pH ~ 8.5 of a solution in contact with newly formed CaCO_3 .

For both organic-containing mixtures the carbonation front was not as well developed at any time point as that observed with water. This made measuring the progression of carbonation with phenolphthalein challenging (Fig. 3). Given that phenolphthalein is a pH indicator, and its use is based on the assumption that a carbonated area is below pH 9, it does not have the resolution to measure areas where both CaCO_3 and $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ are present [6]. Furthermore, as a rapid increase in carbonation was observed by day 21 of the organic-containing pastes compared to the water control, we hypothesize that carbonation is taking place throughout the sample on day 7 and 14, from both atmospheric CO_2 and bacterial CO_2 , but this is not enough to significantly reduce the pH of the sample, making it appear as non-carbonated. This is further supported by the fact that organic additions can be known to improve carbonation and mechanical properties of lime mortars [7].

Fig. 2. Average percentage of carbonation according to phenolphthalein analysis of lime-paste cubes mixed with water, TSB or Sc bacterial suspension. Error bars show standard deviation from at least 3 samples.

Fig. 3. Phenolphthalein analysis of lime-paste cubes mixed with water (A), TSB (B) or Sc bacterial suspension (C) after 21 days. The carbonation front is less clear for the organic-containing pastes than in the case where water was used.

4 Conclusion

It was shown that the use of bacterially-derived CO₂ can be used to carbonate lime-based materials. This opens up an interesting option for organic additives that have shown to be successful in improving overall lime-mortar qualities. Still, when the bacteria were mixed directly with lime the results were less conclusive. Phenolphthalein analysis showed that the lime pastes with water had a better-resolved carbonation front and were observed to be more carbonated. Nevertheless, the fast increase in carbonation observed by the bacterial-lime paste between day 14 and day 21 might imply that carbonation was quickly advancing in this mix as well, although the use of phenolphthalein might not have been the most precise technique for its evaluation.

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